

Cognitive Biases in Information Behavior: From Seeking to Decision-Making

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Abstract: *We live in a complex world that is saturated with information. At every step, at every moment and in every interaction, we make a large number of conscious and unconscious decisions. In the digital age, information is abundantly available, yet individuals often struggle to make objective and well-informed decisions due to cognitive biases. Cognitive biases are mental shortcuts that simplify decision-making but also introduce systematic errors. This article explores the influence of cognitive biases on information behavior, particularly how they shape the processes of information search and selection. Cognitive biases, such as confirmation bias, anchoring, framing effects, and the availability heuristic, impact how users initiate, navigate, and conclude their search for information. These biases often lead individuals to select information that aligns with pre-existing beliefs, overlook alternative perspectives, or rely on easily accessible but potentially misleading data. Ultimately, understanding how cognitive biases shape information behavior is crucial for enhancing decision-making processes, improving information retrieval systems, and promoting a more informed and discerning public in an increasingly information-saturated world.*

Keywords: Anchoring bias, Availability heuristic, Bandwagon Effect, Confirmation Bias, Exposure Effect, Framing Effect, Information Retrieval, Order Effect, Priming Effect, Search Behavior.

1 Introduction

With the widespread availability of digital tools and the internet, information seeking has evolved dramatically. As of April 2025, there are 5.64 billion internet users globally—68.7% of the world's population—who spend an average of 6 hours and 38 minutes online daily. While online activities

range from communication to media consumption, information seeking remains the top motivation, with 62.8% of adults citing it as a primary reason for going online (Digital Around the World, 2025). Platforms like Google process an estimated 8.5 billion searches per day, with 6.3 million queries per minute and over 1 billion voice searches monthly (Dixon, 2025; Jain, 2025). Most of these searches are informational—52.65%, according to Datos—followed by navigational (32.15%), commercial (14.51%), and transactional (just 0.69%) intents (Fishkin, 2024). Search behavior shows adaptability: users often start with short queries of a few words and refine them when the results don't meet their expectations—more frequently on mobile devices than on desktop (Tober, 2022). These evolving patterns highlight the increasing complexity and importance of digital information navigation in everyday life.

In the digital age, understanding how individuals seek and process information is key to comprehending modern information behavior. Information behavior encompasses the various ways people interact with information, particularly through deliberate acts of information seeking, which are shaped by both personal and contextual factors (Chatterjee, 2017). According to Wilson (2000), information seeking is goal-driven and influenced by the seeker's background, the nature of their need, and the resources available. The process of seeking information concludes when individuals feel sufficiently informed to proceed to subsequent decision-making.

The average person makes thousands of decisions every day, most of them unconsciously and guided by mental shortcuts known as heuristics. These shortcuts, while useful, often give rise to cognitive biases that can result in judgments and choices that stray from logic or factual accuracy (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974; Gilovich, Griffin, & Kahneman, 2002; Eldridge, 2023). Cognitive biases are robust and universal psychological patterns that affect judgment and decision-making (Wilke & Mata, 2012; Korteling, Paradies & Sassen-van Meer, 2023). Rooted in predictable cognitive styles, they influence how individuals process and organize information, sometimes resulting in rational outcomes, sometimes leading to poor or suboptimal choices (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973). Individual differences, combined with the mind's limited processing capacity—especially under stress or time pressure—further shape how information is used and decisions are made (Phillips-Wren, Power & Mora, 2019)

Cognitive biases have a profound impact on decision-making across various domains, particularly in health, politics, finance, management, and consumer behavior. In healthcare, bias can lead professionals to overestimate the likelihood of certain conditions based on recent cases, potentially resulting in misdiagnosis (Blumenthal-Barby and Krieger, 2015). In politics, bias often drives individuals to seek information that supports their existing beliefs, impairing objectivity and reinforcing political polarization (Peer & Gamliel, 2013). In finance, cognitive biases can lead to poor investment decisions, as seen in tendencies toward overconfidence or risk aversion (Kumar & Goyal, 2015). Similarly, management decisions are susceptible to biases, which can lead to flawed strategic planning and ineffective leadership (Barnes Jr, 1984). In consumer behavior, emotional attachment, social influence, and marketing tactics often trigger biases that result in irrational purchasing choices. These largely unconscious biases can significantly undermine rational decision-making, often leading to suboptimal outcomes.

Understanding cognitive biases is crucial for improving both information processing and decision-making. As personalization becomes more prevalent in algorithm-driven systems, such as search engines and generative AI tools, understanding the impact of cognitive biases on user behavior is also essential for designing better information systems and decision-support tools that can help counteract

the negative influences of bias. Moreover, awareness of one's own cognitive biases can empower individuals to reflect on and improve their decision-making strategies in both personal and professional contexts.

2 Cognitive Biases

Cognitive biases are unconscious, systematic errors in thinking that affect how individuals perceive, interpret, and act upon information in their environments (Kahneman & Tversky, 1982). Cognitive biases are systematic cognitive dispositions or inclinations in human thinking and reasoning that often do not comply with the tenets of logic, probability reasoning, and plausibility. These intuitive and subconscious tendencies are at the basis of human judgment, decision making, and the resulting behavior. (Korteling, Gerritsma and Toet, 2021)

While cognitive biases are often framed as flaws, they are generally the byproducts of heuristics—mental shortcuts that the brain uses to navigate a complex world efficiently. These shortcuts evolved to help humans make rapid decisions in situations of uncertainty or overload, offering clear evolutionary advantages. The brain is constantly processing a vast stream of information, and heuristics help filter, simplify, and prioritize this input, allowing individuals to respond quickly when necessary (Eldridge, 2023). Heuristics often operate unconsciously, meaning people are typically unaware of the biases that arise from them. According to Kahneman's two-system model of cognition, System 1 governs fast, intuitive thinking and is responsible for many of the snap judgments that lead to cognitive biases. In contrast, System 2 represents slower, analytical reasoning that can override these intuitive judgments with conscious effort (Azzopardi, 2021). However, because engaging System 2 requires time and energy, most daily decisions remain within the domain of the more error-prone System 1.

Since the foundational work of Tversky and Kahneman (1974), researchers have identified over 180 types of cognitive biases. These can be broadly categorized into four major groups based on common mental challenges. First, biases stemming from information overload occur because the brain must rapidly filter massive quantities of data, often ignoring useful information in the process. Second, biases related to the lack of inherent meaning in information arise when the brain attempts to fill in gaps and make sense of fragmented input, sometimes creating false narratives or imagined details. Third, action-oriented biases occur due to the need to act quickly and decisively, which can lead to snap judgments that are unfair or counterproductive. Lastly, memory-based biases reflect the limitations of our recall processes, which often reinforce errors and distortions in future thinking (Benson & Manoogian, 2016). These categories demonstrate the various ways in which cognitive shortcuts, though helpful in navigating complexity, can systematically distort human judgment and decision-making.

3 The Role of Cognitive Biases in Search Behavior

Cognitive biases play a significant role in shaping an individual's information-seeking behavior throughout the entire search process, influencing both the approach to query formulation and the subsequent interpretation of search results. The process of information seeking typically unfolds in four stages: querying, examining result lists, judging result items, and assessing search satisfaction (Azzopardi, 2021). Cognitive biases are evident in each of these stages, from pre-search influences, such as existing beliefs or expectations that guide the types of queries users initiate, to the ongoing

evaluation of results during and after the search. For instance, during the pre-search phase, users' cognitive biases—such as confirmation bias—may lead them to formulate queries that align with their pre-existing attitudes or beliefs. This bias can steer individuals toward certain information sources while dismissing others, thus shaping their entire search experience.

Similarly, during the search process, biases like selective exposure can influence how users interact with search results. Selective exposure refers to the tendency to seek out information that supports one's current viewpoints, both consciously and unconsciously, which can lead users to prioritize links that align with their ideological stance (Robertson, Lazer & Wilson, 2018). As a result, even in algorithmically-driven environments designed to present a range of perspectives, users are likely to engage more with identity-congruent content. The rise of large language models and AI-powered chatbots presents a new challenge, as slight variations in user prompts can yield vastly different results due to their stochastic nature (Röttger et al., 2024). This further emphasizes the complexity of information seeking, as users' intent—the underlying reason for conducting a search—directly affects the types of queries they submit. Consequently, the way users phrase their search queries is influenced by their personal attitudes and information needs, which can further reinforce cognitive biases. The complexity of information seeking is emphasized by how users' intent, attitudes, and information needs shape their search queries, often reinforcing cognitive biases.

3.1 Common Cognitive Biases in Information Seeking

There are numerous types of biases, including several subcategories; however, the following table depicts the most common forms of cognitive bias that influence our search behaviour.

Table 1. Cognitive Biases Influencing Different Stages of Search Behaviour

	Querying	Examining	Judging	Satisfaction
Information overload	Confirmation Bias	Confirmation, Availability, Framing Effects	Confirmation, Anchoring, Availability, Framing Effects	
Lack of meaning	Bandwagon Effect	Bandwagon Effect	Bandwagon Effect, Exposure Effect	
Need to act quickly		Ambiguity Effect	Ambiguity Effect	Less is more
recall/ memory	Priming Effect	Order Effects	Priming Effect, Order Effects	Priming Effect, Peak End Rule

- **Confirmation Bias**

Confirmation bias, commonly defined in psychological literature as the tendency to seek or interpret evidence in ways that favor pre-existing beliefs, expectations, or hypotheses (Nickerson, 1998), remains a significant factor in online information behavior. Evidence suggests that users often prefer search queries that align with their existing attitudes (Ekström, Madison, Olsson & Tsapos, 2024), and there is increasing support for the notion that individuals engage more with attitude-consistent content—a pattern referred to as selective exposure or confirmation bias. For example, experiments by

Knobloch-Westerwick et al. (2015) using simulated search results demonstrated that users not only prefer but also spend more time with content aligned with their views, reinforcing the presence of selective exposure.

- **Anchoring Bias**

Anchoring bias is a cognitive tendency to rely excessively on the first piece of information encountered, which then serves as a reference point for interpreting subsequent information (The Decision Lab, n.d.). This bias leads individuals to assess later data relative to the initial "anchor," rather than evaluating it objectively. In the context of online search, anchoring occurs when the first result on a search engine results page (SERP) shapes users' perceptions of the information that follows (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). For instance, if the top result frames a medical condition as severe, users may continue to view it as such despite later results downplaying its severity. This effect persists even when users are unaware of the influence, often diminishing the level of critical thinking applied to subsequent information (Novin & Meyers, 2017).

- **Availability Heuristic**

The availability heuristic is the tendency to rely on information that is easily available or retrievable from memory rather than seeking out and objectively evaluating all relevant information (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973). This heuristic is influenced by factors such as salience, vividness, negativity, and the primacy-recency effect, which enhance recall and lead individuals to judge the frequency or likelihood of events based on how easily examples come to mind (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973; Dale, 2015). It operates on the assumption that readily recalled information is more important than less accessible alternatives. In the digital age, this effect is amplified by the constant availability of information online, leading individuals to misattribute externally accessible information to their own knowledge—a phenomenon known as the Google Effect—which can reduce the motivation to internalize or rehearse information (The Decision Lab, n.d.).

- **Framing Effects**

The framing effect refers to the cognitive bias in which individuals' decisions are influenced by how information is presented, particularly whether it is framed in a positive or negative light (Framing Effect (Psychology), n.d.). This effect highlights that identical information can lead to different responses depending on contextual cues, such as wording, imagery, emotional tone, or reference points (Framing effect, n.d.). In the context of search engine results pages (SERPs), one form of framing is the document genre (e.g., blog, news report, journal article), which shapes users' interpretations of a source's credibility and purpose (Novin & Meyers, 2017). These framing elements reduce cognitive effort by embedding additional meaning, subtly guiding decision-making through both the content itself and the contextual cues that surround it.

- **Bandwagon Effect**

The bandwagon effect occurs when individuals place disproportionate emphasis on external information while making decisions under conditions of uncertainty (Harris, 2019). This effect, also referred to as herd behavior, subtly shapes user search behavior, particularly through the rapid integration of suggested queries. Users tend to adopt these suggestions more readily when confronted with difficult search tasks or when they do not have much knowledge about the search query, using them as an idea-generation strategy to construct higher-quality queries. Notably, while usage

information may not directly influence selection, the increased reliance on query suggestions underscores the nuanced role of social influence in guiding search behavior without explicitly altering users' selection preferences (Kelly, Cushing, Dostert, Niu, and Gyllstrom, 2010).

- **Exposure Effect**

Exposure effects, closely related to the Bandwagon Effect, occur when repeated exposure to a particular stimulus leads individuals to develop increasingly positive attitudes toward it. (Lau & Coiera, 2007) The frequency and duration of engagement with information reflecting a specific stance or viewpoint can reinforce favorable impressions of that perspective over time. Consequently, when a search engine results page predominantly presents information supporting a single viewpoint, it may influence users to adopt that stance regardless of its accuracy, potentially resulting in biased judgments or flawed decision-making. (Azzopardi, 2021)

- **Ambiguity Effect**

The Ambiguity Effect refers to the tendency for individuals to avoid options with uncertain outcomes, even when those options may offer favorable results. In the context of information search, this bias often manifests as a preference for result items from familiar, trusted sources perceived as reliable, while users are less likely to engage with content from unfamiliar or ambiguous sources. This behavior reflects a cognitive inclination to minimize perceived risk and uncertainty during decision-making processes (Kazai, Craswell, Yilmaz, & Tahaghoghi, 2012).

- **Less is more Effects**

In various everyday contexts, research has shown that presenting individuals with too many options can lead to decision paralysis, reduced decision quality, and lower satisfaction—a phenomenon known as the paradox of choice. If this effect extends to search engine use, it suggests that increasing recall by returning a larger set of results may inadvertently reduce user satisfaction, as users may feel overwhelmed by the volume of choices and struggle to identify the most relevant or appropriate information. (Oulasvirta, Hukkinen, & Schwartz, 2009)

- **Priming Effect**

Priming effects occur when exposure to a stimulus subconsciously influences an individual's response to subsequent stimuli. In the context of information search, these stimuli often take the form of words or images encountered during a search session. For example, the images or search results presented in response to a query can activate certain mental associations, shaping how users perceive and interpret subsequent information. This cognitive activation may, in some cases, lead to unintended and problematic consequences—such as reinforcing offensive, inappropriate, or socially harmful associations—which can then be internalized or further propagated through continued interaction with biased or suggestive content. (Azzopardi, 2021)

- **Order Effect**

Order effects in web search demonstrate that user behavior is strongly influenced by the position of results on a search engine results page. Wu, Jiang, and Zhang (2012) show that clicks follow the serial position effect, with users favoring higher-placed results regardless of their actual relevance. Pan et al. (2007) attribute this to position bias, arguing that users adopt a “fast and frugal heuristic” by trusting top-ranked items, as search engines typically rank the most relevant results first. This trust, they suggest, is learned through repeated interactions and is not irrational. However, Joachims et al. (2005)

identify trust bias and quality bias, where users click more on higher-ranked links even if less relevant, and base decisions partly on position rather than content.

- **Peak End Rule**

The Peak-End Rule bias significantly influences user satisfaction during the search process. As users exert more effort to complete a search task, their satisfaction decreases (Al-Maskari & Sanderson, 2010). Similarly, Kokubu et al. (2005) found that satisfaction diminishes as users examine more results down the rank to find relevant information. Liu and Han (2020) further revealed that user satisfaction is strongly linked to relative gains, losses, and key reference points, with peak and end moments having the greatest impact. The Peak-End Rule suggests that users' evaluations of their search experience are shaped extremely by intense moments (peaks) and the final moments (end), rather than by the overall experience.

4 Strategies for Mitigating Cognitive Biases in Information Behavior

Cognitive biases, deeply ingrained in human thinking, influence how we process, interpret, and act upon information, shaping our decisions and behaviors in ways that are often subtle yet significant. These biases, which have evolved over millennia, are both structural and functional, stemming from neural mechanisms and evolutionary pressures that have historically served adaptive purposes (Korteling & Duistermaat, 2018). However, given their systemic and persistent nature, biases feel natural and self-evident, making them difficult to mitigate through simple educational or training interventions (Korteling, Gerritsma, & Toet, 2021). This inherent limitation calls into question the effectiveness of traditional bias-mitigation strategies, particularly when aimed at long-term or broad decision-making improvements.

Rather than attempting to eliminate these biases, it may be more productive to acknowledge their evolutionary role and adapt strategies that leverage them effectively. While cognitive biases can be detrimental in certain contexts, they are not inherently harmful; rather, they are tools that, when understood and managed correctly, can be beneficial in specific situations (Benson & Manoogian, 2016). Thus, a more realistic approach may involve recognizing that biases are intrinsic to human cognition, and an informed, strategic use of them can lead to more efficient and adaptive decision-making in various contexts. Several approaches can be adopted to counteract the negative influence of cognitive biases in information behavior. These include:

- i. **Awareness:** Developing an awareness of cognitive biases and their influence on decision-making, and using this knowledge to make more informed and objective choices.
- ii. **Critical Information Practices:** using diverse information sources, nurturing critical thinking, and developing a habit of evaluating information with skepticism to counter bias in information selection and interpretation.
- iii. **Search Engine Design Improvements:** Designing search engine results pages that are more neutral and balanced, minimizing the risk of reinforcing biases through skewed or unrepresentative search results.

5 Conclusion

Cognitive bias exerts a profound influence on information behavior, shaping how individuals search for, evaluate, and use information in decision-making. Biases such as confirmation bias, anchoring

bias, availability heuristic, framing bias, and the ambiguity effect often lead individuals to selectively attend to familiar or belief-confirming information while avoiding sources perceived as uncertain or unfamiliar—even when such sources may be valuable. These tendencies are further intensified in digital environments through algorithmic personalization, which curates content based on past user behavior, reinforcing pre-existing beliefs and preferences. Concepts such as the filter bubble and echo chamber underscore how users are increasingly exposed to homogeneous viewpoints, limiting cognitive diversity and entrenching biased perspectives.

Additionally, other biases compound these effects. The exposure effect and Bandwagon Effect cause users to develop more favorable attitudes toward frequently encountered or widely endorsed content, regardless of its accuracy. The less-is-more effect points that too many options can overwhelm users, reducing decision quality and satisfaction—particularly relevant in search environments with high recall. Priming and order effects further influence how users perceive and evaluate information based on its initial framing or its position within a list of results, rather than its intrinsic merit. Finally, the peak-end rule indicates that users often judge the overall quality of an information experience based on its most intense moment and how it ends, rather than on an overall assessment.

Collectively, these cognitive biases highlight the complexity of digital information behavior and may often undermine the accuracy and objectivity of decisions. Recognizing their influence in information behavior is vital for enhancing information behaviour and improving decision quality. Doing so requires a multifaceted approach—creating user awareness, promoting critical information practices, and designing more transparent and diverse information systems that actively counteract personalization and echo chamber effects. Such measures can aid in supporting more balanced and informed decision-making in both personal and societal contexts.

References:

- Alamir Novin and Eric Meyers. 2017. Making Sense of Conflicting Science Information: Exploring bias in the search engine result page. In Proceedings of the 2017 conference on conference human information interaction and retrieval. 175–184. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3020165.3020185>
- Al-Maskari, A., & Sanderson, M. (2010). A review of factors influencing user satisfaction in information retrieval. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61(5), 859-868.
- Azzopardi, L. (2021, March). Cognitive biases in search: a review and reflection of cognitive biases in Information Retrieval. In *Proceedings of the 2021 conference on human information interaction and retrieval* (pp. 27-37).
- Barnes Jr, J. H. (1984). Cognitive biases and their impact on strategic planning. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5(2), 129-137.
- Benson, B., & Manoogian, J. (2016). Cognitive bias cheat sheet: Because thinking is hard. *Better Humans*, 1.
- Berthet, V. (2022). The impact of cognitive biases on professionals' decision-making: A review of four occupational areas. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 802439.

- Blumenthal-Barby, J. S., & Krieger, H. (2015). Cognitive biases and heuristics in medical decision making: a critical review using a systematic search strategy. *Medical decision making*, 35(4), 539-557.
- Chatterjee, A. (2017). Chapter C - Information Users in Elements of Information Organization and Dissemination. Chandos Publishing. pp 47-71, ISBN 9780081020258, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102025-8.00003-X>.
- Dale, S. (2015). Heuristics and biases: The science of decision-making. *Business Information Review*, 32(2), 93-99.
- Deborah Frisch and Jonathan Baron. 1988. Ambiguity and rationality. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making* 1, 3 (1988), 149–157. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdm.3960010303>
- Digital around the world (2025, April). <https://datareportal.com/global-digital-overview>.
- Dixon, S. J. (2025, January 23). *Media usage in an online minute 2024*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/195140/new-user-generated-content-uploaded-by-users-per-minute/>
- Ekström, A. G., Madison, G., Olsson, E. J., & Tsapos, M. (2024). The search query filter bubble: Effect of user ideology on political leaning of search results through query selection. *Information, Communication & Society*, 27(5), 878–894. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2023.2230242>
- Eldridge, S. (2023, March 10). *Cognitive bias | Description & Examples*. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/cognitive-bias>
- Fishkin, R. (2024, December 4). *New Research: We analyzed 332 million queries over 21 months to uncover never-before-published data on how people use Google*. <https://sparktoro.com/blog/new-research-we-analyzed-332-million-queries-over-21-months-to-uncover-never-before-published-data-on-how-people-use-google/>
- Framing effect (psychology). (n.d.). EBSCO Information Services. <https://www.ebsco.com/research-starters/social-sciences-and-humanities/framing-effect-psychology>
- Framing effect. (n.d.). Newristics. <https://newristics.com/heuristics-biases/framing-effect>
- Gilovich, T., Griffin, D., & Kahneman, D. (Eds.). (2002). *Heuristics and biases: The psychology of intuitive judgment*. Cambridge university press.
- Harris, C. G. (2019, June). Detecting cognitive bias in a relevance assessment task using an eye tracker. In *Proceedings of the 11th ACM Symposium on Eye Tracking Research & Applications* (pp. 1-5).
- Jain, G. (2025, January 28). *Jaw-Dropping Google Search Statistics and Facts (2025)*. MageComp Blog. <https://magecomp.com/blog/google-search-statistics-and-facts/>
- Joachims, T., Granka, L., Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., & Gay, G. (2017, August). Accurately interpreting clickthrough data as implicit feedback. In *Acm Sigir Forum* (Vol. 51, No. 1, pp. 4-11). New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow*. Allen Lane and Penguin Books, New York.

- Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1982). On the study of statistical intuitions. *Cognition*, 11(2), 123-141.
- Kazai, G., Craswell, N., Yilmaz, E., & Tahaghoghi, S. M. (2012, October). An analysis of systematic judging errors in information retrieval. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management* (pp. 105-114).
- Kelly, D., Cushing, A., Dostert, M., Niu, X., & Gyllstrom, K. (2010, April). Effects of popularity and quality on the usage of query suggestions during information search. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 45-54).
- Knobloch-Westerwick, S., Mothes, C., Johnson, B. K., Westerwick, A., & Donsbach, W. (2015). Political online information searching in Germany and the United States: Confirmation bias, source credibility, and attitude impacts. *Journal of Communication*, 65(3), 489–511. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12154>
- Kokubu, T., Sakai, T., Saito, Y., Tsutsui, H., Manabe, T., Koyama, M., & Fujii, H. (2005, December). The Relationship between Answer Ranking and User Satisfaction in a Question Answering System. In *NTCIR*.
- Korteling, J. E., Gerritsma, J., and Toet, A. (2021). Retention and transfer of cognitive bias mitigation interventions: a systematic literature study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 629354. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.629354
- Korteling, J. E., Paradies, G. L., & Sassen-van Meer, J. P. (2023). Cognitive bias and how to improve sustainable decision making. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1129835.
- Korteling, J.E., and Duistermaat, M. (2018). Psychological Deception. Report TNO R11532. Soesterberg: TNO Defence, Safety and Security.
- Kumar, S., & Goyal, N. (2015). Behavioural biases in investment decision making—a systematic literature review. *Qualitative Research in financial markets*, 7(1), 88-108.
- Lau, A. Y., & Coiera, E. W. (2007). Do people experience cognitive biases while searching for information?. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 14(5), 599-608.
- Liu, J., & Han, F. (2020, July). Investigating reference dependence effects on user search interaction and satisfaction: A behavioral economics perspective. In *Proceedings of the 43rd international ACM SIGIR conference on research and development in information retrieval* (pp. 1141-1150).
- Oulasvirta, A., Hukkinen, J. P., & Schwartz, B. (2009, July). When more is less: the paradox of choice in search engine use. In *Proceedings of the 32nd international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval* (pp. 516-523).
- Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., Joachims, T., Lorigo, L., Gay, G., & Granka, L. (2007). In Google we trust: Users' decisions on rank, position, and relevance. *Journal of computer-mediated communication*, 12(3), 801-823.
- Peer, E., & Gamliel, E. (2013). Heuristics and biases in judicial decisions. *Ct. Rev.*, 49, 114.
- Phillips-Wren, G., Power, D. J., & Mora, M. (2019). Cognitive bias, decision styles, and risk attitudes in decision making and DSS. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 28(2), 63-66.
- Raymond S. Nickerson. 1998. Confirmation bias: A ubiquitous phenomenon in many guises. *Review of General Psychology* 2, 2 (1998), 175–220. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.2.2.175>

- Robertson, R. E., Lazer, D., & Wilson, C. (2018). Auditing the personalization and composition of politically-related search engine results pages. *Proceedings of the 2018 World Wide Web Conference*, 955–965. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3178876.3186143>
- Röttger, P., Hofmann, V., Pyatkin, V., Hinck, M., Kirk, H. R., Schütze, H., & Hovy, D. (2024). Political compass or spinning arrow? Towards more meaningful evaluations for values and opinions in large language models (arXiv:2402.16786). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.16786>
- Shad, R., Olukemi, A., & Potter, K. (2024). The Impact of Cognitive Biases on Consumer Decision-Making. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*.
- The Decision Lab. (n.d.). Why do we compare everything to the first piece of information we received?. <https://thedecisionlab.com/biases/anchoring-bias>
- The Decision Lab. (n.d.). Why do we forget information that we just looked up?. <https://thedecisionlab.com/biases/google-effect>
- The Think with Google Editorial Team. (2024, november). *How well do you know Google Search?*. <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/marketing-strategies/search/google-search-innovations/>
- Tober, M. (2022, October 25). *Zero-Clicks study*. Semrush Blog. <https://www.semrush.com/blog/zero-clicks-study/>
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1973). Availability: A heuristic for judging frequency and probability. *Cognitive psychology*, 5(2), 207-232.
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1974). Judgment under Uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases: Biases in judgments reveal some heuristics of thinking under uncertainty. *science*, 185(4157), 1124-1131.
- Wilke, A., & Mata, R. (2012). Cognitive bias. *Encyclopedia of Human Behavior (Second Edition)*. Academic Press. pp. 531-535, ISBN 9780080961804, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-375000-6.00094-X>.
- Wilson, T. D. (2000). Human information behavior. *Informing science*, 3, 49.
- Wu, M., Jiang, S., & Zhang, Y. (2012, October). Serial position effects of clicking behavior on result pages returned by search engines. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management* (pp. 2411-2414).